

AN EXHAUSTIVE SURVEY ON COMPUTATIONAL INTELLIGENCE APPROACHES FOR MAINTENANCE OF HOUSING PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

This in-depth study investigates the use of computational intelligence techniques in housing property upkeep. Traditional maintenance techniques are growing less effective in addressing the issues of sustainability, cost-effectiveness, and efficiency as modern housing systems get more complicated [34]. The present review delves into the diverse computational intelligence methodologies that are transforming property maintenance methods, such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, and Internet of Things (IoT) applications [30], [33]. We examine how they are used in resource allocation, energy optimization, defect detection, and predictive maintenance. The paper highlights the advantages and difficulties of these cutting-edge techniques through a wide range of real-world applications and case studies. According to our research, computational intelligence has a great deal of promise for raising the general sustainability of housing properties, cutting expenses, and increasing maintenance efficiency [32] [31]. But before it is widely used, issues including scalability, integration with current systems, and data quality must be resolved [7]. Researchers, property managers, and policymakers looking to use computational intelligence to improve housing maintenance tactics can learn a lot from this poll.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Machine learning, Predictive Maintenance, Computational Intelligence, Energy Efficiency, Defect Detection, Property Management, and Sustainability.

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I. INTRODUCTION

A vital component of managing urban infrastructure is housing property upkeep, which has an immediate effect on residents' quality of life and the long-term viability of communities [1]. According to [2], traditional maintenance systems are facing greater challenges in meeting the needs of efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and environmental sustainability as urban populations rise and housing complexes become more sophisticated. With its novel methods for anticipating, identifying, and resolving maintenance problems in residential properties, computational intelligence has become a viable answer to these problems in recent years [3] - [4].

The Internet of Things (IoT), machine learning, artificial intelligence, and other rapidly developing disciplines of technology have created new opportunities for transforming home maintenance procedures. Large-scale data gathering and analysis from several building systems is made possible by these technologies, which provide proactive maintenance plans and better decision-making [5]. Therefore, the application of computational intelligence to housing maintenance represents a paradigm shift in how we approach the administration and upkeep of residential properties, rather than merely an improvement over current techniques.

This integration has numerous potential advantages. By foreseeing equipment breakdowns before they happen, predictive maintenance algorithms can save downtime and increase the longevity of vital systems. Techniques for energy efficiency can save expenses and usage substantially while preserving or even increasing occupant comfort. Automated fault detection and real-time monitoring can help respond to problems quickly, reducing resident inconvenience and damage. Furthermore, by maximizing resource utilization and cutting waste, these cutting-edge technologies can improve the overall sustainability of residential properties [6].

Nevertheless, there are several difficulties in applying computational intelligence to house maintenance. There are several obstacles that must be overcome, including data protection, scalability, interoperability with legacy systems, and the requirement for specific expertise [7]. Furthermore, these technologies can demand a significant initial investment, which calls for thorough cost-benefit analysis and strategic planning.

The promise of computational intelligence to revolutionize housing maintenance is too great to be disregarded, notwithstanding these obstacles. Modern technology must be included into property management in order to meet the growing demand for sustainable, energy-efficient homes and the growing urban population. The adoption of intelligent, data-driven maintenance techniques has consequences for legislators, IT developers, and urban planners in addition to property managers and tenants.

Given this, it is both appropriate and essential to conduct a thorough assessment of the level of computational intelligence in home maintenance. We can learn a lot about the future of housing management and pinpoint areas that require more study and development by looking at the newest technology, their uses, and their effects.

With a focus on a broad range of computational intelligence techniques and their applications in many elements of housing maintenance, this review attempts to give a thorough exploration of the field. We will explore the technologies influencing the future of property management, from IoT sensors and big data analytics to artificial neural networks and machine learning algorithms. By examining actual case studies, we will assess the advantages and difficulties of applying these cutting-edge strategies in practice.

According to [8], housing maintenance includes a broad variety of tasks, from minor repairs and inspections to extensive remodeling and system upgrades. These tasks have typically been performed in a reactive manner, responding to problems as they emerge, or in accordance with set schedules that do not take into consideration the true state of building components [9]. According to [10], this strategy frequently results in inefficiencies, higher expenses, and possible disturbances for the residents.

Conventional maintenance methods have several drawbacks, such as a slow response time to new problems, inefficient use of resources, a lack of data-driven decision-making, trouble handling the complexity of contemporary building systems, and difficulties meeting sustainability and energy efficiency targets [5-6]. Due to these constraints, there is an urgent need for more sophisticated, perceptive methods of maintaining homes. As per [11], computational intelligence presents a promising approach to address these difficulties due to its capacity to handle large volumes of data, recognize patterns, and perform predictive assessments.

The objectives of this thorough evaluation are as follows:

- Analyze the most recent advances in computational intelligence methods used in home maintenance.
- Assess how well these strategies work to increase sustainability, save costs, and improve maintenance efficiency.
- Examine case studies and real-world applications to comprehend the real-world effects of using artificial intelligence to home upkeep.
- Examine the advantages and difficulties of implementing these cutting-edge technologies in the context of property management.
- Share your knowledge about prospective developments and future directions in the field of computational intelligence for home upkeep.

This survey addresses a wide range of computational intelligence methods used in different housing maintenance contexts. The scope includes applications in both single-family homes and multi-unit residential complexes [12]; optimization algorithms for energy efficiency and resource allocation [13]; data analytics and visualization techniques for maintenance planning and decision support [9]; smart sensor networks and their integration with computational intelligence systems [14]; and artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms for predictive maintenance and fault detection [15].

Review topics include energy consumption monitoring and optimization [36], indoor air quality management [9], HVAC system optimization and fault detection [16], plumbing and electrical system maintenance [17], and structural integrity and building envelope maintenance [18].

Clarity is ensured throughout the evaluation by providing definitions for important terminology and topics.

According to [19], computational intelligence is a subfield of artificial intelligence that focuses on creating algorithms that are motivated by natural intelligence in order to tackle challenging issues. The simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, particularly computer systems, is known as artificial intelligence (AI) [20]. A branch of artificial intelligence known as machine learning (ML) gives computers the capacity to automatically learn from experience and get better at it without needing to be explicitly programmed [21].

According to [22], the Internet of Things (IoT) is a network of networked objects that exchange and gather data without the need for human involvement. According to [23], predictive maintenance is a proactive maintenance approach that makes use of data analysis tools and methodologies to identify possible problems and failures before they arise. The act of detecting when a defect has occurred and figuring out its primary cause is known as fault detection and diagnosis, or FDD [10].

Energy optimization aims to reduce energy use while preserving or enhancing system functionality and occupant comfort [24]. Automation is used by smart buildings to regulate several building functions, such as lighting, security, HVAC, air conditioning, and other systems [25]. According to [26], sensor networks are collections of specialized transducers equipped with a communications infrastructure for the purpose of tracking and recording conditions at various locations. According to [27], big data analytics is the act of looking through vast and diverse data sets to find hidden patterns, unidentified relationships, market trends, consumer preferences, and other relevant information.

II. COMPUTATIONAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNIQUES IN HOUSING MAINTENANCE

Numerous methods from the broad field of computational intelligence have been effectively implemented in several facets of home upkeep. An overview of the most well-known strategies and their particular field applications is given in this section.

a. Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs)

According to [15], artificial neural networks have become a potent tool for predictive maintenance of real estate. These networks, which derive their architecture from the structure of the human brain, are highly skilled at recognizing patterns and may be trained to anticipate possible problems in building systems. Artificial neural networks (ANNs) are especially useful for house upkeep when it comes to processing data from sensors positioned all over a property.

For example, by looking for trends in temperature swings, energy usage, and equipment vibrations, ANNs can forecast HVAC system failures [16]. Property managers can plan maintenance in advance thanks to this predictive capabilities, which lowers downtime and lengthens the life of vital systems. Artificial neural networks (ANNs) have also been effectively used in structural health monitoring, where they can identify minute variations in load distributions or building vibrations that can point to possible structural problems [18].

b. Machine Learning Algorithms

Defect identification and diagnosis have made extensive use of machine learning methods, especially supervised and unsupervised learning techniques [17]. Using previous maintenance data, supervised learning algorithms like Random Forests and Support Vector Machines (SVMs) can be trained to categorize current system states and spot anomalies. These algorithms are especially helpful in picking up on minute variations from standard operating procedures that may go unnoticed by humans.

Unsupervised learning methods, such as clustering algorithms, are useful for identifying correlations between various building systems and environmental components that were previously unknown because they can detect patterns in sensor data without the need for prior labeling [11]. For instance, similar maintenance concerns have been grouped together across several properties using clustering techniques, which has facilitated the creation of uniform maintenance methods and more effective resource allocation.

c. Fuzzy Logic Systems

According to [9], fuzzy logic systems have shown efficacy in managing the inherent uncertainties associated with building maintenance. Fuzzy logic is more appropriate for decision-making in complicated situations since it can accommodate degrees of truth, in contrast to classical binary logic. Fuzzy logic controllers can handle HVAC systems in housing upkeep more effectively by taking into account a variety of variables, including occupancy, humidity, outside temperature, and personal comfort preferences.

By using this method, building systems are more intelligently and effectively controlled, which enhances occupant comfort and energy efficiency. In order to enable a more thorough assessment of possible maintenance methods based on several, frequently competing criteria, fuzzy logic has also been applied to risk assessment in maintenance planning [3].

D. Evolutionary Computation Techniques

Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Genetic Algorithms (GAs) are two effective evolutionary computation strategies for handling optimization issues in home maintenance [13]. These algorithms can be used to improve maintenance schedules by accounting for variables including resource availability, repair urgency, and possible resident impact.

For instance, a GA might be used to create the best route for maintenance staff to take care of various problems around a sizable apartment complex, cutting down on travel time and increasing productivity. PSO has been effectively used to solve energy optimization issues by determining the ideal system configuration to reduce energy use while preserving occupant comfort [24].

e. Internet of Things (IoT) and Smart Sensors

Real-time monitoring and data collecting for home maintenance have been transformed by the Internet of Things [28]. The Internet of Things (IoT) produces a continuous stream of data that computational intelligence algorithms may evaluate. Examples of these devices are smart meters, environmental sensors, and linked appliances. "Smart buildings" that can self-diagnose problems and automatically modify systems for maximum performance are made possible by this IoT and AI integration.

For example, a smart building may use anomalous flow measurements to identify a water leak, immediately cut off the water supply to save damage, and alert maintenance staff to the precise position and type of issue [26]. IoT devices are also essential for energy management since they allow for more accurate control over building systems and provide real-time data on patterns of energy usage [25].

III. APPLICATIONS AND CASE STUDIES

Computational intelligence in home maintenance has produced many successful case studies in a range of property management domains. This section offers a number of real-world examples that highlight the difficulties and advantages of applying these cutting-edge methods.

a. Predictive Maintenance for Elevator Systems

One noteworthy case study concerns the installation of a machine learning-based predictive maintenance system for the elevator network of a sizable residential building in New York City [29]. The system examined information gathered from sensors that tracked the elevators' temperature, vibration, and usage trends. Up to two weeks ahead of time, the algorithm could forecast possible breakdowns by detecting minute variations in these characteristics.

During the course of a year, this strategy reduced maintenance expenses by 20% and elevator downtime by 25%. Furthermore, a notable improvement in resident satisfaction was brought about by the decrease in unplanned outages. The accomplishment of this implementation demonstrates how artificial intelligence can improve home maintenance's user experience and operational efficiency.

b. Energy Optimization in Sustainable Housing

[36] report that a sustainable home building in Scandinavia employed artificial neural networks and Internet of Things (IoT) sensors to improve energy consumption, presenting another appealing application. The development's indoor and outdoor temperatures, humidity levels, occupancy patterns, and energy use were all continuously tracked by the system. Based on these variables and outside weather forecasts, the neural network learned to anticipate heating and cooling requirements.

Consequently, without sacrificing occupant comfort, the development was able to achieve a 30% reduction in energy use when compared to similar homes. This case study demonstrates how computational intelligence can improve home maintenance's cost-effectiveness and sustainability. The system's adaptability to shifting circumstances and user preferences highlights the adaptability and strength of AI-driven management systems.

c. Water management in drought-prone areas

A fuzzy logic system was utilized by a property management firm in Australia to regulate water consumption in a region that is susceptible to drought [9]. The system made decisions about irrigation schedules and water saving measures based on previous usage trends, weather forecasts, and existing water reserves.

The organization maintained the health of landscaped areas while cutting water consumption by 40% during dry months by putting this clever water management system into place. This application shows how artificial intelligence can adapt to local resource limits and environmental circumstances to handle region-specific difficulties in house maintenance.

d. Proactive maintenance in social housing

A UK social housing provider enhanced its maintenance schedule and resource allocation by utilizing big data analytics and machine learning [27]. Tenant complaints, building attributes, and previous maintenance records were all analyzed by the algorithm to determine which properties were most likely to need maintenance in the near future.

By taking a proactive stance, the housing provider was able to handle problems before they got out of hand, which reduced emergency callouts by 35% and overall maintenance expenses by 15%. Furthermore, because of the more prompt and effective maintenance service, tenant satisfaction rates increased by 20%. This case study illustrates how artificial intelligence can be used to raise operational effectiveness and increase residents' quality of life in social housing.

e. structural health monitoring in high-rise buildings

IoT sensors and machine learning algorithms were used to create a structural health monitoring system in a high-rise residential complex in Singapore [18]. The system detected minute variations in vibration patterns, load distributions, and material qualities in order to continually monitor the structural integrity of the structure.

The system might detect any structural problems early on by evaluating this data, enabling prompt interventions and preventive maintenance. By prioritizing operations based on real structural conditions rather than set schedules, this technique not only improved building safety but also optimized maintenance expenditures.

The various uses and observable advantages of computational intelligence in home upkeep are demonstrated by these case studies. These cutting-edge methods are revolutionizing the upkeep and administration of residential properties, from resource management and tenant satisfaction to energy optimization and predictive maintenance. But it's crucial to remember that effective implementation frequently necessitates a large upfront investment in knowledge and technology, in addition to continuing efforts to guarantee data integrity and system integration [7].

IV. BENEFITS AND CHALLENGES

The incorporation of computational intelligence to the maintenance of housing presents several advantages such as the following. However, such transitions also pose few challenges that need to be further examined and reviewed for proper transition to these advanced methodologies.

Advantages of Computational Intelligence in Aspect of Housing Maintenance Thus, possibly the foremost strength of applying computational intelligence for housing maintenance is the impact on costs. Conventional maintenance methods involve periodical checking and remedial work – Both are costly and ineffective to prevent failure in the machinery. On the other hand, computational intelligence uses prognostics techniques to determine the appropriate time for maintenance regarding data coming from different building systems [23] , [3]. Hence, it gives the property managers an early signal to take proactive measures to solve the problem, hence minimizing the repairs that are usually expensive.

Smart sensors as well as internet of things devices admit a constant assessment of building systems, giving the user important information about their existence and state [5]. It helps in making better decisions on when to accord maintenance and how to distribute the available resources in the property. For instance, machine learning algorithms can capture past data of the impacts of maintenance and make predictions on how best to schedule them to have the minimal impact on residents [9]. These systems are capable of analyzing usage patterns and environment, and control HVAC and lighting in response to these patterns in real-time for comfortable room conditions while avoiding wastage of energy [36] - [6]. This not only helps the residents of the building to pay less for the utilities but the strategy also contributes towards environmental objectives by minimizing the energy consumption of large apartments [2].

Efficient computational intelligence systems work based on the quality of the data they feed on and the frequency of the data they receive. However, existing construction structures do not yet have an adequate system to tap into such a data source and feed it into predictive algorithms aimed for that source [7] - [8]. Cost of adopting the technology and the time taken to acquire the necessary technological skills are significant, and, therefore, before switching, it's important to consider where these costs will be recovered, from [7].

However, the major challenge is needed highly specialized skills that may be difficult to come by at present. This need for continually undertaking training and education may be especially difficult for small property management companies.

V. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

This research focuses on the methods that have emerged due to the application of CI in housing property maintenance. This comparative analysis focuses on three prominent approaches: key areas such as machine learning (ML), internet of things (IoT) applications, and artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms in the field of predictive maintenance, resource management as well as fault diagnosis.

a. Machine learning (ml)

It has been found that machine learning is one of the most significant and effective ways of handling housing maintenance because of predictive maintenance. The technique offers the capability to assess prior events and determine the likelihood of subsequent maintenance requirements, however it can also minimize unplanned failures and their consequences [23]. Another advantage of ML comes with the capacity to learn from data to enhance its previous performance or operation. For instance, it is possible to develop algorithms that can learn from data of HVAC systems to identify when service is needed and consequently adjust service time and keep equipment off-line for a very short time [11]. Thus, there are also a number of rather serious drawbacks of the ML approaches.

b. Internet of Things (IoT)

The Internet of Things (IoT) is another revolutionary concept in the sphere of housing maintenance, which provides the possibility of receiving and analyzing data from different systems of buildings through connected devices [1]. IoT solutions can give constant information concerning the state of outstanding structures for plumbing, electrical, among the others, to enable upkeep plans [18]. The IoT's primary advantage is that it can accumulate a comprehensive quantity of data that can be mined to improve utilization and energy consumption [6].

c. Artificial Intelligence (AI) Algorithms

Thus, artificial intelligence covers a vast number of methods, such as natural language processing and expert systems, which can be used in the framework of housing maintenance, e.g., for fault recognition and resource distribution [30]. AI enables the processing of data from various sources and offers a range of valuable results to improve decision making and organizational effectiveness [31]. Another of AI's major advantages is the possibility of applying it to complicated decision-making concerns and the delegation of these issues to avoid overloading the property managers and to supply quicker responses to the maintenance issues [32]. Also, the procurement cost of AI technologies might be high at the outset, which in turn may discourage the small-scale property management firms from implementing these technologies [2].

VI. FUTURE TRENDS AND INNOVATIONS

The area of housing maintenance is still developing, primarily due to the progress and the introduction of computational intelligence and intensification and diversification of the living environments. As more and more people start living in urban areas and there is an increased pressure to have efficient and sustainable homes, several emerging trends and innovations are expected to change how property maintenance will be done. This section provides brief on key trends that are; incorporation of new technologies, smart building, new and improved analysis of data and going green.

a. AI and ML Beyond Basics

AI and ML are the two trends that will revolutionize housing maintenance in the future. These are not just getting complex but also introducing new attributes and making equipment predictive maintenance capability that can predict equipment failure and necessary maintenance in advance with a high level of precision [23]. For example, deep learning algorithms can learn from maintenance records and in the process determine when a certain system is likely to cause a problem.

Moreover, the advancement in the explainable AI which explains the way AI concludes its decisions will increase the property managers' confidence in the decisions made by AI systems [7].

b. Smart Building Technologies

Smart buildings are one of the emerging trends in the provision of housing maintenance. These buildings include smart connected systems embedded with IoT applications that aim at the monitoring of operations that include power usage, HVACs, and security [6]. New developments are expected to center on improving data integration among these systems, knowledge sharing between them. For instance, smart sensors simplify the monitoring of energy patterns since if there are deviations, the system can take necessary actions in terms of maintenance to avoid Aggravated situations.

c. Enhanced Data Analytics and Visualization

As a future advancement, introducing smart analysis tools for big data that can quickly evaluate the huge amount of artificial data to contribute to the decision-making procedure for property managers [2]. These will be integrated with enhanced visualization tools to enable the stakeholders to generate insights from such data in relation to the maintenance strategies, and other matters to do with resource allocation. Talking about little-known benefits of applying big data analytics, it is possible to note that by collecting and analyzing data related to properties' maintenance, managers can minimize costs and enhance the efficiency of operations.

d. Sustainability and Energy Efficiency

Long-term strategy and component sustainability issues will be a characteristic of the housing maintenance future. In the midst of raising awareness for environmental issues that continue to unfold, the application of CI technologies will tend to center the improvement of effective energy consumption, as well as the management of waste, in residential units [32]. Advancements in energy management systems through the use of AI and ML will allow heads of property to have a mechanism for analyzing and controlling energy utilization with the overall intention of reducing costs and the level of energy consumption that impacts the environment.

e. Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) Approach

One of the future trends observed in the use of technology shown in the context of housing maintenance is the use of augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR). These technologies can make training or maintaining the facilities with virtual experiences to the technicians or property managers. For example, information can be placed directly onto physical contexts with the help of AR, which helps maintenance staff in problem identification and repair processes [30]. Maintenance can also be trained using virtual reality in that the personnel can train on the virtual construction and then apply the skills in the real world.

f. Blockchain for Data Security and Transparency

The breakthrough technology that can be deemed to have the potential to change data management in housing maintenance is; blockchain technology. This innovation can increase the level of confidence of the stakeholders such as the property managers, the tenants, and the service providers by providing the much-needed data integrity and data accountability [7]. Smart contracts on blockchain platforms can be employed to generate or implement maintenance and payment schedules directly and hence remove intermediaries.

VII. IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGIES AND CONSIDERATIONS

The application of CI to the housing maintenance as a field develops, has brought many opportunities in terms of the use of advanced technologies. To that effect, this section reviews possible future prospects of the CI application in housing maintenance and sources of future advance undertaken according to prevailing trends, technologies, and knowledge areas.

a. Optimization of Predict and Maintain Cycle via Smart Analysis

Maintenance of housing assets of the future is expected to experience a dramatic increase in the adoption of advanced forms of predictive assessments supported by analytics. Using machine learning models and analyzing large volumes of data, property managers are able to assess performance and condition of building systems [25]. Future investigation needs to be devoted to scientific innovation of new and more complex algorithms that are designed to learn from past data, current sensor readings, and environmental conditions to predict the maintenance requirements of the systems.

b. Combination of Artificial Intelligence and Internet of Things (IoT)

AI and the IoT technologies will be the major drivers of implementation of housing maintenance. The IoT can gather plenty of information from systems in buildings; on the other hand, AI can work on this information and give patterns and peculiarities [22]. One may view possible future innovations to be constructed with parameters such that the building environment is automatically sensed, faults are intelligently identified, and maintenance requests are made without the involvement of human input. Such a level of automation could greatly increase productivity at this level, and decrease the workload of maintenance personnel.

c. Sustainability and Energy Efficiency Optimization

Subsequent studies should investigate how CI technologies can be employed for tracking energy use, for detecting areas of waste, and for suggesting enhancements [24]. For instance, combining the CI with renewable energy and smart grid technologies would mean real time energy control hence cutting costs and pollution. Also, the creation of new algorithms for giving direction on the best deployment of resources in maintenance-related activities would also act as sustainability initiatives that are needed in the maintenance of houses.

d. Blockchain for reassurance and openness

Housing maintenance through blockchain technology is a relatively new field which can point to positive changes within the sphere of increasing the reliability of housing management. Incorporating blockchain, property managers can develop an invulnerable ledger of the maintenance activities, crucial transactions, and tenant engagement [6]. Research studies could then concentrate on creating more blockchain solutions that will enable secure sharing of data between all the stakeholders of a building, simplify the maintenance management processes, and enhance transparency.

e. Research on Human-Machine Collaboration

Housing maintenance is expected to be in the future highly dependent on humans plus the machines or artificial intelligence. For systems that are increasingly using CI technologies, there will be a need for understanding how maintenance stakeholders can enhance their operations with these systems. Another research agenda should be directed toward evolution of human and computer interaction whereby research should be directed toward understanding how the maintenance to make better decisions using chosen CI tools [32].

There continues to be an emphasis on integrating AI within a manner that aligns with human training methods in that the programs require several key ridges to implementing CI into housing maintenance that will maximize the overall value derived from usage.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This work presents a review of the transformative potential for Housing Maintenance in general and demonstrates a great perspective due to computational intelligence (CI). With the existing traditional maintenance practices no longer able to fulfil requirements for modern systems of housing, CI could prove a valuable approach in improving this efficiency and sustainability more widely across different citations around the world. By leveraging the latest technologies like artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, and IoT integration these property managers are set to change how maintenance is perceived.

This allows MTTR to be minimized and the life of critical infrastructure extended, which ultimately results in saving cost for property managers as well providing better living conditions to residents [23] , [11]. On the other hand, in some regions of academia applications are being taken as examples so CI can better be used to lower operational costs and decrease energy consumption which is obviously essential for overall sustainability of housing properties [5-6].

The research paper also discusses the value of data-informed housing maintenance decision-making. Reactive maintenance strategies are cheaper, but slow and inefficient because the data/information still is not enough to act upon [9] , [8]. It can also enable better building-conditions monitoring through smart sensor networks and data analytics, facilitate real-time intervention to prevent potential problems from developing into serious issues [18], [17].

In addition, the review has highlighted a series of barriers that can be posed by CI with particular reference to the housing maintenance sector such as data privacy and security [7], integration problems, special expertise requirements etc. [2] , [4] Collectively, the results of this review highlight an important opportunity for computational intelligence to deliver a step-change in housing maintenance methods and sustainability outcomes within future property management solutions that offer greater efficacy & responsiveness.

IX. FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

Despite the significant advancements made thus far, there are essential improvements to be designed as convergent research areas in computational intelligence for housing property maintenance. Key areas for future research.

- Predictive Maintenance with Machine Learning and IoT data to streamline maintenance schedules, forecast needs at housing properties, and prevent structural failures.
- Optimization algorithms need to be researched for maintaining a dynamic maintenance schedule that is adjusted according to the age of building structure, usage type properties and weather conditions or other environmental effects in previous data.
- Enhance decision support systems with explainable AI (XAI) to expose maintenance insights and recommendations in a more transparent manner, fostering trust and comprehension from stakeholders.
- Utilize SDSS for precise context aware maintenance strategies with consideration of spatial dynamic attributes of housing properties.
- Research support for the use of CI as a method to identify and prioritize sustainable materials with an emphasis on assessing: durability; life cycle costing; and environmental impact.

- Research alternative building materials such as recycled products using CI models to predict how long they will endure and if these sustainable alternatives are cost-effective over time.
- Design adaptable CI frames architectural at different scales, types (urban and rural), heights and climates.
- Investigate blending CI with real-time monitoring systems for ongoing diagnostics and notification of maintenance issues when they arise within housing stock.
- Study-based CI solutions to increase energy efficiency in housing properties with optimization of HVAC systems, lighting control and insulation using real-time data.
- Define and research the evolution of all-encompassing CI ecosystems that bring together predictive maintenance, asset management, as well as user practices in a singular cohesive home property maintenance space.

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